
ISAAC SIM INTEGRATED DIGITAL TWIN FOR FEASIBILITY CHECKS IN SKILL-BASED ENGINEERING *

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ABSTRACT

Skill-based engineering is an approach to encapsulate complexity of control software into reusable and parameterisable components. Digital Twin (DT) technologies can be applied to predict the future behaviour of the skills enabling feasibility checks for specific action requests. In this work, we introduce a methodology for combining NVIDIA's Isaac Sim framework for high quality DT-based simulations with an interoperable control component integration based on ROS and OPC UA. Furthermore, we demonstrate skill-based robot feasibility checks, which apply physical control (Hardware-in-the-Loop), virtual control (Software-in-the-Loop) as well as combinations of both.

Keywords Skill-based Engineering · Feasibility Check · Simulation · Digital Twin · Isaac Sim · OPC UA

1 Introduction

Global manufacturing in complex supply chains together with the increasing need for customisation of products with high variability leads to an enormous cost pressure in the factories. This applies both to the production processes themselves and to the underlying technical processes. Proposed solution approaches in the context of Cyber-Physical Production Systems (CPPS) are tackling efficient reconfiguration by a modular production structure, standardised connectivity as well as encapsulation and reuse of software components. Recent developments are referring to Digital Twins (DT) as representation of a physical asset, which can be utilised for analysis, simulation, and optimisation of production lines as well as for the unification of information exchange [1]. One attempt for the reuse of control components is the skill-based approach, where the behaviour of mechatronic devices such as machines and robots is described by encapsulated software functions with unified interfaces [2]. In combination with a DT integration, a forecast of the asset behaviour can be achieved, which can be incorporated into a feasibility check of the required action.

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However, this requires high quality multimodal DTs capable of simulating physical reality as well as their integration with the state-of-the-art communication and information modelling technology. Isaac Sim developed by NVIDIA offers rich modelling and simulating capabilities that are foundational for creating a physics-based DTs. This makes Isaac Sim a potential candidate for the DTs development. However, it further requires good integration with industrial equipment.

In this work, we propose an approach for integrating an Isaac Sim-based virtual environment with a ROS2 driven robot along with the OPC UA skill model for implementing feasibility checks in the scope of skill-based engineering. The paper is structured in the following way. Section 2 gives an overview of the current skill-based approaches both in the manufacturing and robotics domains, as well as the application of DTs in industry. In section 3 we describe our approach for integrating DTs in the feasibility checks for the skills, while in section 4 we provide the implementation details. Further, section 5 discusses the opportunities of the method as well as the challenges that need to be solved. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 State of the Art

Recent developments of skill-based engineering are directed to encapsulation of software functions for production, handling, transport and human-robot-interaction and related DT integrations.

2.1 Skill-based Engineering in Manufacturing and Robotics

Froschauer et al. have listed in [3] the expected benefits of using skills in manufacturing, such as flexibility and planning efficiency in production, development efficiency, reuse, and interoperability. Koecher et al. in [4] have provided a reference model for a common understanding of skills, capabilities, and services in the manufacturing domain. A capability is “an implementation-independent specification of a function to achieve an effect in the physical or virtual world”. Capabilities are meant to be implemented by so-called skills and then offered as services in supply chains. A skill is “an executable implementation of an encapsulated (automation) function specified by a capability.” By explicitly separating capabilities from skills, it is possible to decouple the description of a function from its implementation. Skill’s interface exposes its behaviour through a harmonised state machine, as well as input and output parameters.

In the last few years, several prototypes have shown the applicability and benefits of using skill-based design for modular, plug-and-produce capable production systems [5, 6, 7, 1]. The use of standard state machines in these prototypes eases integration efforts, while OPC UA information modelling and communication capabilities improve interoperability. Volkman et al. in [1] have extended the skill model with the feasibility check and the context check to verify beforehand if the required skill can be successfully started. Wagner et al. in [2] have demonstrated the interactions between the feasibility check, the context check, which they called precondition check, and the skill’s execution state machine, with the focus on the skill-based machining.

In the robotics domain, skill-based design of the control software focuses on code reusability and modularity, as well as separation of roles during the development process. Skills are reusable components that encapsulate expert knowledge in some task, e.g., in trajectory planning. An approach for task-level programming of flexible mobile manipulators in industrial environments has been proposed in [8]. The authors have defined the terminology of tasks, skills, and motion primitives and shown how this can be used to separate the responsibilities of the robot software developers. Rovida et al. have defined a robot skill as a fundamental software block, which changes the world state [9]. An operator configures a robot by defining a scene and a goal, and the robot plans the required sequence of skills to achieve the goal.

Although the authors in [1] and [2] stress the importance of simulation for the implementation of the feasibility check, few has been done for the integration of the simulation-based skills feasibility checks into the skills models. As we show in this paper, a combination of Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) and Software-in-the-Loop (SiL) simulations, as well as the use of the standard OPC UA based skill interface can fill the gap.

2.2 Digital Twins

Digital twins (DT) have shown benefits in different industries, spanning between manufacturing and energy sectors, and agriculture and retail [10]. They are helpful in different stages of the manufacturing industry, showing its potential from designing smart manufacturing systems (SMSs) to optimising their performance [11]. Wang et al. showed that monitoring and allocating resources in shared manufacturing through digital twins is possible. Geng et al. demonstrated how coupling DT with Augmented and Virtual Realities (AR/VR) promoting Human-Machine-Interaction [12].

Digital twins come in different forms which fundamentally differ in levels of communication. (1) Digital models, (2) Digital Shadows and (3) Digital Twins [13]. Each of the mentioned types of DT can be used as the basis for different simulations. Digital shadows can be used to conduct SiL simulations, where algorithms can be tested on

running real-life scenarios through streaming information from the physical environment into the digital environment. Additionally, it is possible to carry out HiL testing where robot agents and their controllers are utilised for different virtual scenarios through DTs [14]. A combination of both can also be used in the context of DTs facilitating feasibility checks and accordingly taking action. This is carried out by acquiring data from the physical environment and digitally testing algorithms for new process steps and scenarios without risking downtime, thus aiding in generating new process plans smoothly [15].

To this day, described implementations rely on model-based DTs. Combinations of different modelling frameworks like OpenModelica, MATLAB and Simscape were used to create digital models as well as incorporating them to DTs. However, they often result in rigid, unscalable solutions [16, 17, 18]. Physics engines like Unity have also been experimented with authoring DTs especially due to its capability to create high fidelity rendered models which are essential in digital environments [19] and achieving high accuracy, low-latency performance [20]. Nevertheless, it must be stated that these were only methodological studies that do not include functional DTs. Gazebo being a more common, compliant with robotics, physics engine was also used to create DTs that communicate through different communication virtual commissioning [21] and OPC UA for comparing different DT control approaches [22]. Even though there exist functional implementations for physics-capable DTs, limitations like using rigid models, the lack of embedding the physical environment into the virtual model or the absence of a unified interface for both environments are common to face.

3 Methodology

The overall methodology is based on a combination of three preliminary approaches which are integrated into a reference structure for robot testing, commissioning and control. The first part is the unification of skills using the OPC UA information model for describing variables and methods. The second part is the design of a reference control structure and the integration of Isaac Sim, ROS and OPC UA software components. The third part is related to the exchangeability of physical asset and DT.

3.1 OPC UA Model of a Robot's Skill

The OPC UA model of a robotic arm shown in figure 1 is based on SmartFactory-KL² OPC UA nodeset of a cyber-physical production module (CPPM). This model is used for all the CPPMs in the SmartFactory-KL demonstrators ecosystem and serves as their standard cyber-representation. This greatly improves interoperability between various control platforms and ensures independence from the automation hardware vendors. The skill model is described in all detail in [1] and [2]. We highlight only the most important features.

Figure 1: OPC UA model of a robot's skill.

First, it can be noticed that the skill (OPC UA node *Pick* in figure 1) consists of two similar parts: *SkillExecution* and *FeasibilityCheck*. The *SkillExecution* part provides an interface to the robot's controller. The interface is represented by the standard state machine *StateMachine*, the set of parameters *ParameterSet* used to parametrize the robot's controller,

²<https://www.smartfactory.de/en/>

and the *FinalResultData* that provides the results of skill's execution. The FeasibilityCheck part is connected to the robot's DT and provides several functionalities: first, it triggers the path planning process to generate the robot's collision free trajectory and simulates the movement; second, if the movement has succeeded it provides as part of its FinalResultData the Feasibility_ID that references the generated robot's trajectory, which can be further used by the robot. As both interfaces are almost identical, the skill requester (in our case, it is an OPC UA client) can use the real and the simulated parts of the skill in the same manner.

3.2 Digital Twin Integration

The digital environment is based on Isaac Sim, which provides data from virtual sensors and mirrors the physical system. Isaac Sim's embedded workflows can be adapted and exploited in numerous ways based on the desired use case. In addition to its library of various types of robots from different vendors, Isaac Sim can import any URDF file to the simulation stage. Furthermore, its architecture makes it possible to make user-defined extensions. An extension can be viewed as a customised library designed for a specific objective, which may range from incorporating libraries into the Isaac Sim runtime to modifying the physics scene and component parameters. Isaac Sim natively offers ROS 1/2 bridges to utilise ROS messages for synchronisation of virtual agents with physical ones or even controlling real hardware from within the simulation environment. Having access to a ROS-driven environment allows using off-the-shelf ROS packages from different robot vendors and the ROS community for rapid integration with various controllers and solving planning problems.

As further demonstrated in section 4, our proposed architecture utilises ROS2 for low-level robot real as well as virtual control. The digital twins of the environment, the robot, and its gripper are loaded in the simulation stage of Isaac Sim. The virtual functionality is activated by the OPC UA server, which we have embedded into Isaac Sim, and uses the ROS-actions mechanics for controlling DTs. The proposed approach seamlessly combines both real and virtual robot functionality in a simulation environment and provides it as one standard OPC UA model.

3.3 System Structure and Component Integration

Figure 2 shows a block diagram of the implementation prototype. The goal of this setup was to test a hybrid HiL-SiL framework and lay the groundwork for DT-based FeasibilityCheck functionality to the OPC UA based robot skills.

The physical setup consists of a robot UR5e without a gripper. The robot is controlled using the publicly available ROS2 package from the vendor. The MoveIt2 package generates motion plans for a given target pose and uses the robot's controller interface for controlling the arm. As shown in figure 2 an action server has been developed to encapsulate the MoveIt move group low-level functionality and is capable of providing similar MoveTo actions for, both, the real and the virtual robots when needed. The ur_driver package from the UR5e vendor can work both in real and virtual modes. In real mode, it controls the UR5e through the RTDE interface and publishes the states of the robot's joints to the special topic for monitoring. In virtual mode, it simulates the robot's movements and just publishes the joint states to the monitoring topic which is subscribed to by the ROS2 bridge of Isaac Sim where it is used for moving the DT.

As the basis for a digital twin, a UR5e digital model with a Robotiq 2f-85 gripper attached to its flange was used in Isaac Sim. The damping and stiffness values for each robot's joint were modified, as the default values result in a stalling robot. To control the robot in the simulation environment, an OmniGraph Action Graph has been created to facilitate the motion of the DT robot. As mentioned earlier, the Action Graph uses the joint states information from ur_driver as input to Isaac Sim's articulation controller that consequently mirrors the real robot's movement in the digital environment. For now, in the implemented proof of concept, the gripper is controlled using Isaac Sim python API to open and close. However, a ROS2 action server can be later used in the same way as described for the robot's action server as shown in figure 2 .

The abovementioned was wrapped in an extension that is created using the provided, by NVIDIA, base template for extensions. The extension contained Isaac Sim's environment and the in-house developed OPC UA server based on the python-OPC UA stack ³. During startup, the extension loads the Universal Scene Description (USD) stage file of the DT and starts the OPC UA server that encapsulates available skills for the robot agents in both environments altogether; the robot arm and gripper in this case.

4 Robot Skill Use Case Implementation

As part of our proof of concept, the OPC UA server is loaded with a nodeset containing *move* and *grip* skills. Where the former behaves in the same manner as described before, controlling the real robot and mirroring its state in the DT and

³<https://github.com/FreeOpcUa/opcua-asyncio>

Figure 2: Block diagram of the proposed approach.

the latter triggers the gripper control function in Isaac Sim’s Python API to control the virtual gripper, thus introducing a mixture of HiL and SiL simulations side by side as shown in figure 3. In this implementation, the robot is commanded to move to a desired pose and actuate the virtual gripper to grasp. Thus, facilitating the exploitation of the existing robot controller with another virtual robot agent for task execution and validation. Such a combination helps to avoid any deviations from a simulated behaviour that may potentially cause a failing task execution while opening doors for testing different scenarios that include different objects and agents virtually.

5 Discussion

The approach proposed in this work creates several opportunities as well as challenges for creating skill-based CPPS. First, efficient integration of high-quality multimodal DTs with robots is beneficial as it provides them predicting capabilities to better act in the unstructured and changing environments. ROS2 enables easy and rapid integration of various robot types from different vendors. Isaac Sim provides rich virtualisation capabilities for creating DTs. The approach is modular and allows separate development of the system components. Second, the Isaac Sim DTs provide the means for implementing simulation-based feasibility checks and parametrisation of the robotic skills. Such feasibility checks are physics-based and visualisable, which increase system transparency and creates thrust from a user. Third, the approach allows various scenarios of running HiL and SiL simultaneously in the hybrid virtual and real environments. This creates truly interesting opportunities for CPPSs in further integration of cyber and physical. Lastly, using the information modelling and communicating capabilities of the OPC UA technology enables seamless integration between DTs and CPPSs. It should also be noted that the approach can be scaled further to the production cells and lines.

Nevertheless, to apply the approach in real industrial environments, several challenges must be faced. First, to directly use the results of the simulation in reality, such as a generated movement trajectory for a robot, we require very precise

Figure 3: Capture of running HiL/SiL implementation.

calibration and synchronisation between the DT and its real-world counterpart. The second challenge that relates to the first one is to constantly monitor how close the simulated and the actual system variables are. For this, we envision in our system a deviation monitor that compares the joint state values coming from the real robot with the simulated ones generated by the virtual `ur_driver` (see figure 2).

6 Conclusion

The approach presented in this work utilises simulating capabilities of the Isaac Sim virtual environment in combination with the ROS2 robotic middleware versatility and the OPC UA communication and information modelling functionalities to enhance the skill-oriented design of the robotic control software. The proof of concept implementation demonstrates feasibility of the method. Though still in prototype phase, the approach creates opportunities for enhancing skill-based control in robotics and CPPS.

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